

Development of the Gas Safety Management System using an Intelligent Gasmeter with Wireless ZigBee Network

Gyou-tae Park†, Young-gyu Kim, Jeong-rock Kwon, Yongwoo Lee, Hiesik Kim*

Abstract—The gas safety management system using an intelligent gas meter we proposed is to monitor flow and pressure of gas, earthquake, temperature, smoke and leak of methane. Then our system takes safety measures to protect a serious risk by the result of an event, to communicate with a wall-pad including a gateway by zigbee network in buildings and to report the event to user by the safety management program in a server. Also, the inner cutoff valve of an intelligent gas meter is operated if any event occurred or abnormal at each sensor.

Keywords—micom gas-meter, gas safety, zigbee, ubiquitous

I. INTRODUCTION

THE modern and high class apartments are equipped with safety devices at facilities of gas, electricity and water. It is clear that a sensor will make our lives safer and more comfortable in the future. We can use it as not only a fire alarm or a gas leak detector, but also a biochemical attack watcher [1, 7]. We propose a gas safety management system using an intelligent multi-function gas meter, which include ZigBee network technology, automatic gas leak cutoff, sensors of smoke, methane, and temperature. At first we developed the intelligent micom-gas-meter which has a built-in cutoff valve and sensors of flow, pressure, and earthquake [2]. That gas meter operates its inner valve and shut off the gas, serving a warning on users if any unusual is occurred for gas flow, pressure, earthquake, temperature, and leakage (methane and CO) in gas pipeline and facilities [3]. Our gas safety management system is configured by the topology of star types with those devices and sensors and then controls all the devices through a wall-pad including a gateway with ZigBee network [4, 5], and takes safety measures to protect a serious risk. In this paper, the proposed system used EM250 ZigBee chips and ZigBee PRO stack [6] and improved the performance of gas

safety Gas safety management system, compared with CC2430 chips [3].

A. The intelligent gas meter (Micom gas meter)

The micom-gas-meter, a kind of gas meter, built in a micro-controller and a cutoff valve, is not only to measure gas flow and pressure but also to monitor earthquake. This instrument can open and close an inner cutoff valve and serve a warning on users if it is uncommon for flow, pressure and earthquake sensors in gas facilities and houses [2]. Fig. 1 shows the appearance of a micom-gas-meter with a wireless ZigBee communication module including EM250.

Fig. 1. The appearance of a micom-gas-meter with wireless module

Fig. 2. Components and functions of a micom gas meter

In Fig. 2. the components of a micom gas meter are showed. The micom gas meter consists of mechanic type gas meter adding to a built-in cutoff valve and electronic safety functions, which include cutoff of mass and cumulative, instantaneous rising and descending flow rate, high and low pressure, and an earthquake measuring 3.0 on the Richter scale and alarming and buzzer functions [2]. Table 1 appears safety functions which a micom gas meter can intelligently control itself.

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Fig. 6 shows a small test bed to experiment operated conditions of a micom gas meter, methane detector, external gas valves through a wall-pad with ZigBee network. In Fig. 7, types of experimental data are showed. The state of cumulative flow rate is abnormal if flow rate is exceeded limit installed in advance. The instantaneous rising flow rate can be occurred if gas pipeline is cracked and flow rate is abruptly increased.

Fig. 6. Experimental devices and Performance Test

Fig.7. Experimental types for functions

IV. CONCLUSION

We developed a micom gas meter with built-in ZigBee devices and configured ZigBee network to control micom gas meters. We verified that gas safety management system using a micom gas meter can be used to protect an incident effectively. The proposed system takes safety measures while monitoring flow, pressure, and earthquakes in parts of gas facilities and then inform dangerous situations to users as a message through mobile devices. In near future, components of gas, electric, water, and fire safety instruments can be controlled by a ubiquitous sensor network. Our system, then, can be applied to ubiquitous city infrastructure on gas safety management and rise the efficiency of energy safety and reduction. Hopefully, gas incidents are gradually disappeared for our efforts [8].

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